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Practical Education of Quantum Engineers

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INTRODUCTION

We are currently in the midst of a technological transition commonly termed “the second quantum revolution”. Building on advancements in our ability to control,

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² ulrich.hoff@fysik.dtu.dk generated probabilistically into separate spatial modes. By detecting a photon in one mode, a single photon is conditionally prepared in the other mode.

manipulate, and detect quantum objects, accumulated over the past decades, quantum physics phenomena such as entanglement and superpositions are now employed as resources for novel quantum technologies such as quantum computers, quantum cryptography, and quantum sensors. Expectations are high, and the emerging technologies are foreseen to impact and benefit society at large. However, there is a shortfall of creative and innovative quantum engineers with an in-depth grasp of quantum physics and practical experience with the relevant experimental techniques, who can bridge the gap between fundamental science and engineering and take a lead in the quantum innovation process. This was also a central issue in the *Quantum Manifesto* [1] which paved the way for the recently launched EU FET Flagship on Quantum Technologies.

Here, we report on the recently initiated undergraduate course “Experimental techniques in quantum technology”, held at DTU Physics in January 2017. Targeting practical education of quantum engineers, the course implements elements of the CDIO (Conceive-Design-Implement-Operate) framework [2] and stimulates creative and innovative problem solving in the context of quantum technology. The task we pose the students is: *Pick a quantum technology, implement it, and make it operational in 3 weeks!*

1 COURSE PREPARATIONS

In the following sections we summarise our considerations about the learning objectives for the course and how to enable the students to meet the set goals within the framework of the course.

1.1 Learning objectives

A key role for quantum engineers will be to merge research and technology. This requires a profound understanding of quantum physics, its experimental implementation and the techniques involved, and not least the ability to explain and discuss both theoretical and practical aspects of an experimental setup. Equally important skills for quantum engineering, belonging to the core of engineering in general, relate to participation in teamwork efforts towards practical solutions to concrete bounded problems. Those are exactly the competences the CDIO framework seeks to enhance through project-based learning. Last but not least, an engineer working in quantum innovation should be careful and meticulous about her work and able to document and justify all actions taken on the grounds of empirics and analyses. Those are basic requirements for engineering and research in general, but even more so for emergent technologies where the competition is strong and possibilities for taking out patents should be kept in mind.

The above considerations were condensed into a set of learning objectives for the course as presented below. Except for the subdivision into categories of objectives, the learning objectives given in the course description were exactly as follows:

A student who has met the objectives of the course will be able to:

(Quantum engineering specific objectives)

- *Transform elements of quantum theory into practical quantum technology*
- *Analyse the properties of quantum light sources*
- *Explain the different techniques used in a particular quantum technology*
- *Discuss experiments in quantum optics*

(CDIO related objectives)

- *Diagnose and evaluate technical imperfections in experiments*
- *Identify, design and implement optimal data analysis strategies*
- *Organize, plan and carry out collaborative work in group projects*

(General scientific and engineering related objectives)

- *Document experimental lab work*
- *Present and defend experimental work*

1.2 Resources and course plan

At DTU Physics we have recently established an educational facility, which enables students to gain hands-on experience with some of the phenomena underpinning quantum technologies through advanced quantum optics experiments. The facility includes 5 sets of commercially available experimental setups (Figs. 1 & 2) which offer students the opportunity to investigate on their own e.g. the phenomenon of quantum entanglement via tests of Bell's inequality with entangled photons [3].

Fig. 1 quED entanglement demonstration setup from qutools GmbH.

Fig. 2 A look inside the quantum light source that generates entangled photon pairs in the quED setup.

Apart from quantum light sources capable of delivering both heralded single photons² and entangled photon pairs, the experiments also include avalanche photodiodes (APD) for single photon detection, manual and automated polarisation

² A pair of photons is generated probabilistically into separate spatial modes. By detecting a photon in one mode, a single photon is conditionally prepared in the other mode.

optics, and data acquisition. In the context of the course, the setups constituted the experimental backbone, giving students access to research grade systems and technologies and enabling hands-on creativity about implementation of quantum technologies. During the course, the experimental setups were relocated to a dedicated teaching environment for which the students had all-day access. This was done with the purpose of facilitating build-up of an intense and intimate innovation atmosphere that stimulated teamwork and technological creativity. Furthermore, the infrastructure at the department provided access to the following resources throughout the course: a broad selection of measurement equipment, electronics, a supply of optics components, fine mechanical workshop, 3D printing, and a high performance computing infrastructure for data analysis.

The course was designed for a 3-weeks period, and a total workload corresponding to 5 ECTS credits or 138 hours. The CDIO structure is inherent to the task we posed the students, but to make the structure more visible and force the teams to set deadlines for their progression stages, it was also implemented in the course schedule. The planned structure for the course is summarised in Table 1.

Table 1: Tentative course structure

Phase	Description
0	<p><i>Course start (day 1)</i> Pre-test (written questionnaire and assignments) to gauge students' theoretical and experimental background in quantum physics and their proficiency in programming, instrumentation/data acquisition, data analysis, and documentation/presentation.</p> <p>Introductory lectures on quantum key distribution (QKD) [4] and quantum sensing with NOON states [5] including a number of problems the students could choose to address for each technology.</p> <p>Hands-on experience with experimental setups.</p>
1	<p><i>Problem selection / Team formation / "Conceive" (day 2-3)</i> Formation of project teams (3-4 people) based on chosen problems.</p> <p>Conceiving of the actual problem to be solved through discussions and literature study.</p>
2	<p><i>"Design" (day 4)</i> First iteration of problem solution and plan for experimental implementation.</p>
3	<p><i>"Implement" (ramp-up end of week 1 + week 2 + beginning of week 3)</i> First implementation ► experimental feedback ► re-iteration of design ► modification/extension of implementation.</p>
4	<p><i>"Operate" (week 3)</i> Demonstrating the feasibility of the implemented solution. Data acquisition.</p>
5	<p><i>Preparation for evaluation (end of week 3)</i> Summary of problem, chosen strategy, actual work done, and faced challenges. Selection of key results and data to present. Preparation of poster.</p>

Since students from different departments and hence with different educational backgrounds and experiences was expected to attend the course, a pre-test was prepared for the first day to gauge their proficiency in areas central to the course.

Subsequently, a brief introduction to quantum technology was given together with more detailed presentations of the two emerging technologies selected for the course and central issues for those. On that basis the students were asked to choose what technology to work on and form project teams of up to 4 people. Throughout the remainder of the course, no lectures were scheduled and the authors took the role of supervisors rather than teachers. Upon request from the students, short lectures introducing new theoretical or experimental concepts were given when required for the further progression of the teams. Each team was requested to keep a detailed logbook documenting their progress, data, and internal discussions and considerations about how to solve problems or what strategy to follow. Once every day a brief supervision meeting was held with each team, for which they were requested to prepare a short summary of the findings, progress and challenges of the previous day.

Due to the open curriculum of the course and the focus on process rather than achieving a pre-defined goal, a passed/not passed evaluation form was chosen. The final evaluation was arranged in the form of a mini conference open to the rest of the department. Each team was required to present their quantum technology and document and defend the progress made towards an implementation of it in the format of a scientific poster. In addition to the continuous discussions with the teams, this enabled an evaluation of the students' understanding of their topic and ability to engage in a discussion of it and thereby assess their ability to meet the general scientific learning objectives.

2 COURSE REALISATION

In the end, 7 students attended the course. Given the pilot test character of the course and the amount of experimental equipment available, this turned out to be a very suitable number. Three teams were formed, two teams (2 and 3 people) working on QKD and one team (2 people) working on quantum sensing.

During the design phase, it became clear that the two different types of projects involved challenges of very different character. Whereas the quantum key distribution projects required the students to make only small modifications to the existing setups, but a vast amount of programming for automation, data acquisition, and analysis, implementation of quantum sensing required that team to layout and construct an entirely new optical setup. As our undergraduate students are generally very skilled and experienced in programming but much less so in experimental optics and laser physics, this enabled the QKD teams (Fig. 3) to advance much faster than the quantum sensing team (Fig. 4). In the end the latter team did not manage to achieve a successfully operating system. The design was implemented but they were unable to demonstrate the expected quantum-enhanced performance. Despite

the disappointment of several failed attempts, the team maintained a constructive and enthusiastic approach. After realising that they would not be able to reach the 'operate' phase within the given time frame, they took a step back to discuss, reconsider and re-iterate the design. This was an important example of how the process-oriented and active approach to learning can turn negative results into a precursor for deep learning [6].

In contrast to the negative results on quantum sensing, the efforts on QKD were much more fruitful and resulted in operational systems implementing the B92 protocol [7]. Furthermore, the teams were able to proceed with investigations of quantum properties of the system such as photon indistinguishability via Hong-Ou-Mandel interference [8], measurements of the second order quantum coherence of the employed heralded single photon source [9], and characterisation of the total detection efficiency.

Fig. 3 Discussion of the QKD system performance.

Fig. 4 The quantum sensing team implementing their interferometer design.

Characteristic for the entire course was that all participants showed a very high level of engagement and motivation for the projects and appreciation of the "real-world" problems and challenges associated with the practical approach to quantum engineering. This was confirmed by the students' answers to a Course Experience Questionnaire at the end of the course. On a scale 0-5, the questions '*Course stimulated enthusiasm for further learning?*' and '*Course motivating?*' both got an average score of 4.57. On the other hand, the problem-based approach and the responsibility for progression and learning being with the teams themselves, somewhat disconnected the students from the syllabus. This was reflected in an average score of 3.71 to the question '*Having a clear idea about where to go and what was expected?*'. A related concern was expressed in a comment from one of the students: '*The course schedule was very vague and too open.*' This should be kept in mind for future courses and addressed through the supervision process and a clear introduction to the CDIO framework. Such planning and structure related issues result from the teachers' lack of experience with implementation of CDIO. As one of the students added: '*It was obvious to us that it was the first time the course was*

taught'. However, despite the shortcomings the students' overall evaluation of the course was generally positive as exemplified by the statement: *'All-in-all a good 3-weeks quantum course which I am sure will become really great after a few trials'*.

3 CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

In conclusion, we have prepared and conducted a first pilot testing of a problem-based undergraduate course on practical education of quantum engineers, building on the CDIO structure and principles. The motivation was to establish a frame for creative and innovative thinking about practical implementation of quantum technologies that fosters deep learning and can be used as a boot camp for training the next generations of quantum engineers.

The experiences acquired so far are generally very promising, as are the evaluations and feedback from the students. We are confident that the problem-based approach is an adequate way to stimulate quantum innovation while at the same time creating awareness of the associated real-world technical problems and challenges. With only 7 students attending this first and so far only iteration of the course, the evaluation data is, however, unarguably wanting in quantity. Several consecutive runs with a large course volume would be required for development and documentation of a successful implementation of CDIO principles in quantum engineering education. Larger course volumes and faculty involvement would also allow for an increased focus on industry relevant aspects such as project management and introduction of project sponsors [10]. However, the highly specialised components required for harnessing quantum phenomena for technological innovation poses an economical barrier for up-scaling the course volume as the costs for establishing suitable workspaces (CDIO Standards 6) are immense. As quantum technologies mature, this issue could partly be resolved through industry-based projects [11] co-financed by the involved industry partners. From an educational point of view, this would enable learning in a real-world context, while for the industries a rather small investment would buy a valuable link to fundamental research, currently driving the quantum innovation process, as well as a unique opportunity for early recruitment of quantum engineers.

It is clear that a single project-based course is insufficient for spurring quantum innovation. Hence, we believe the curriculum for a future quantum engineering study programme should give students at least two encounters with the CDIO approach, cf. CDIO Standards 5. The 3-weeks period, in which the present course was given, is suitable for a first experience with project-based learning and could address any part of the basic engineering curriculum or an interdisciplinary cross-field of several [12]. This should then be followed by a long-term (full semester) project, preferably industry-based, specialised on a particular quantum technology. Combining existing theoretical courses at DTU Physics, which provides students with profound theoretical understanding of quantum physics, with a series of progressively challenging CDIO projects would constitute a strong and inspiring framework for

educating engineers with optimal skills for advancing the field of quantum technology.

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